

THEORETICAL PROBLEMS OF LEXICAL SYNONYMY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7198906>

It is known that the scope of work done on the phenomenon of linguistic synonymy in the XX century is significant compared to the work done in world linguistics. Separate scientific collections, serious studies, and monographs were created in this regard. For example, in the monograph published in Russian lexicography in the late XX - early XXI century and analyzed about 3,200 different types of dictionaries, about 50 synonym dictionaries in the Russian language were scientifically commented in detail, and their achievements and shortcomings were noted.

Despite this, there is not a single scientific view that is uniform in revealing the complex essence of synonymy in world science. Russian linguists N.V. Koroleva and E.V. Artamonova note several different definitions of synonyms put forward by different linguists, i.e. synonyms are "lexical units corresponding to one or more lexical meanings" (T .I. Arbekova); "words with the same meaning, but different pronunciation" (N.G. Goltsova); "words that express the same concept, but differ from each other in terms of semantics (facets of meaning) or stylistics" (A.M. Chepasova); "words not only related to the same subject, but also close in meaning, they have a common lexical meaning" (V.I. Kodukhov) "words with the same meaning" (M. Maruzo); "words with similar meaning" (L.R. Zinder, T.V. Stroeva); "words expressing the same concept or very close concepts" (A.P. Evgenyev); "words with a single or very close subject - logical content" (K.V. Arkhangelskaya); "words that are identical in nominative essence, but usually stylistically different" (A.A. Reformatsky); "words that can replace each other in a specific context or contexts close in content" (L.A. Bulahovsky).

When looking at these definitions, it is clear that it does not give an opportunity to get into the inner part of the linguistic industry. Synonymy is deeply studied at the lexical, morphological, syntactic and stylistic levels.

In Uzbek linguistics, special monographs devoted to this phenomenon (lexical synonyms are taken into account) began in the 60s of the XX century.

It should be noted separately that the description of the phenomenon of synonymy in Uzbek linguistics is noteworthy for its comprehensiveness. This definition belongs to the famous linguist academician A. Hojiyev, in which a number of subtle aspects of synonymy have found their clear and clear

expression: "The sameness of the meaning of synonyms does not deny that they have different characteristics.

On the contrary, the presence of several words to express the same meaning in the language shows that synonyms are not fully compatible in all respects; each of them has its own characteristics. Since the words that make up the synonymous series differ from each other in some respects, they have the opportunity to live as a separate lexical unit in the language", the wholesale linguistic reserve called synonyms would be a completely redundant and unnecessary burden on the language.

Uzbek linguistics has accumulated a lot of experience in dealing with the problems of synonymy, and there have been various studies in this regard. The first views about the phenomenon of synonymy in the Uzbek language and the mutual meaning relations between language units that occurred during this phenomenon are devoted to the illumination of the direction of lexicology of the Uzbek language, and a textbook created for use at various stages of education and expressed in manuals. Fakhri Kamol's "Uzbek language lexicon" and "Current Uzbek language lexicon" and "Current Uzbek literary language", "Uzbek language" by M. Mirzayev and others, "Current Uzbek literary language" of the authors' team, two-story", "Current Uzbek literary language" by U. Tursunov and others, "Some issues of the lexicon of the Uzbek language" by U. Tursunov and N. Rajabov, Sh. The academic publications "Current Uzbek Literary Language" and "Lexicology of the Uzbek Language" by Shoabdurahmanov and others can be cited as an example. The linguistic nature of Uzbek language synonyms was also the object of special monographic research. S. Isamuhamedova and R. Doniyorov wrote their candidate theses on the subject of synonymy. Articles written in Uzbek linguistics about synonymy are also a significant amount. Unfortunately, it is not possible to list them all here. Just mention the literature "Uzbek language stylistics and speech culture" compiled by R.Kongurov and S.Karimov and "Uzbek language stylistics and speech culture" organized by S.Karimov and T.Zhorayev our among them, M.Rakhmatullayeva's candidate's dissertation on the topic "Regarding the study of synonyms in the Alisher Navoi language" is worth noting.

Academician A. Hojiyev gave a unique definition to the phenomenon of synonymy, having studied a number of views that are widespread in linguistics. Professor Y. Tajiyev tried to give a different definition of this phenomenon, relying on the definitions and interpretations that appeared in Russian and European linguistics after the 70s of the XX century, not only referring to dictionary synonyms. A. Hajiyev says that "words with the same unifying meaning, pronunciation and spelling, as well as different shades of additional meaning are considered

synonyms", Y. Tajiyeв says that "some of the meanings of separate units in the language The linguistic phenomenon formed by the similarity of names is called synonymy", he says. Synonymy is deeply studied at the lexical, morphological, syntactic and stylistic levels.

Definitions of synonyms in Uzbek linguistics were initially based on the sameness of their meanings, then their commonality, and then their similarity (exactly). Most of the early definitions of synonymy relied on the same meaning. More precisely, when defining synonymy, researchers initially considered their meanings as an indivisible unit. Professor S. Karimov in his monograph entitled "Artistic style of the Uzbek language" made important comments about synonyms: "The phonetic construction (form) is different, but the meaning is the same: to rotate - wander - walk, pedagogue - teacher". Synonyms are one of the important opportunities for those who use them, in particular, poets, writers, and journalists, to express the same concept with different nuances of meaning. The works of A. Doniyorov, A. Hojiyev, R. Kongurov are of special importance in the study of synonyms. G.R.Rakhmonov's thesis submitted for receiving the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in philology studies the phenomenon of gradation among synonyms.

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